

Sum of the Summation of Binomial Expansions with Optimized Binomial Coefficient

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Abstract: This paper presents the summations of binomial expansions with the optimized binomial coefficients and also the sum of multiple summations of the binomial coefficients. This combinatorial result is useful for researchers who are working in computing, science, engineering, and management.

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1. Introduction

Combinatorial and computing techniques [1-9] use the binomial coefficients, combinatorial expansions, factorials, and integers for the applications in science, computing, communication and cybersecurity [1-3]. The traditional binomial coefficient and optimized binomial coefficient and its relationships are given below. The optimized binomial coefficients [4-10] are used for the development of the binomial expansions and series constituted on the multiple summations of geometric series [11-17].

Let $N = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots, \}$ be the set of natural numbers including zero element.

Traditional binomial coefficient: $nC_r = \binom{n}{r} = \frac{n!}{r!(n-r)!}$, where $n, r \in N$.

Optimized binomial coefficient: $V_r^n = \frac{(r+1)(r+2)(r+3)\dots(r+n)}{n!}$, ($n \geq 1, r \geq 0$ & $n, r \in N$).

The optimized binomial coefficient is $V_x^y = V_y^x$. Let $z = x + y$, where $x, y, z \in N$.

The traditional binomial coefficient $zC_x = zC_y = \frac{z!}{x!(z-y)!} = \frac{(x+y)!}{x!y!}$.

Here, $V_n^0 = V_0^n = nC_0 = nC_n = 1$ & $V_0^0 = 0C_0 = \frac{0!}{0!} = 1$.

2. Binomial Expansion

Theorem: $\sum_{i=0}^0 V_i^{0-i} + \sum_{i=0}^1 V_i^{1-i} + \sum_{i=0}^2 V_i^{2-i} + \sum_{i=0}^3 V_i^{3-i} + \dots + \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} = 2^{n+1} - 1$

where $V_n^0 = V_0^n = nC_0 = nC_n = 1$ & $V_0^0 = 0C_0 = \frac{0!}{0!} = 1$.

Proof. $V_0^0 = 1 \Rightarrow \sum_{i=0}^0 V_i^{0-i} = 2^0$; $\sum_{i=0}^1 V_i^{1-i} = V_0^1 + V_1^0 = 2^1$;

$$\sum_{i=0}^2 V_i^{i-i} = V_0^2 + V_1^1 + V_2^0 = 2^2; \sum_{i=0}^3 V_i^{i-i} = V_0^3 + V_1^2 + V_2^1 + V_2^1 + V_3^0 = 2^3.$$

Similarly, we can continue this process upto n such that $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} = 2^n$.

When making the summation on both sides, we get

$$\sum_{i=0}^0 V_i^{0-i} + \sum_{i=0}^1 V_i^{1-i} + \sum_{i=0}^2 V_i^{2-i} + \sum_{i=0}^3 V_i^{3-i} + \dots + \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} = \sum_{i=0}^n 2^i,$$

where $\sum_{i=0}^n 2^i = \frac{2^{n+1} - 1}{2 - 1} = 2^{n+1} - 1$ is the geometric series [18, 19].

$$\therefore \sum_{i=0}^0 V_i^{0-i} + \sum_{i=0}^1 V_i^{1-i} + \sum_{i=0}^2 V_i^{2-i} + \sum_{i=0}^3 V_i^{3-i} + \dots + \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} = 2^{n+1} - 1.$$

Hence, theorem is proved. Corollary

$$\text{Corollary: } \sum_{i=0}^k V_i^{k-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{k+1} V_i^{k+1-i} + \dots + \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} = \sum_{i=k}^n 2^i = 2^{n+1} - 2^k.$$

3. Conclusion

This article has provided the summations of binomial expansions with the optimized binomial coefficients and also the sum of multiple summations of the binomial coefficients. These combinatorial and computing results are useful for researchers who are working in science, engineering, management, and medicine [16, 17].

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